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Continuing Pedagogical Education in the Conditions of Digitalization: The Risks of Alternative Society

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Abstract

The theoretical and methodological foundations of the approach to the study of the continuity of pedagogical education are presented on the basis of an analysis of the risks of the impact of digitalization on the development of the personality of students and their socialization, including the emergence of new types of communication (communication in instant messengers; communication with a computer, etc.). The main characteristic of the continuity of education is considered the viability of the student in unity with the viability of the teacher. The article presents a system for reducing the risk of communication of schoolchildren in the virtual space (bullying, trolling by classmates, and / or unknown people), which ensures the viability of the teacher – the mediative space of the educational organization. At the same time, each of the participants in this space has its own leading predictor of vitality: the teacher has spirituality, and the student has self-actualization. The methodological approaches and models presented in the article allow to solve the problem of reducing the aggressiveness of the educational space on the basis of improving the viability of both teachers and students.

Keywords: alternativeness, risks, riskology, continuity, digitalization, viability, cyber-socialization, mediation.

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Introduction

Continuity of education is considered as a purposeful process of mastering knowledge and sociocultural experience throughout life. The contemporary sociocultural situation in Russia by philosophers, sociologists, political scientists is defined as an alternative one associated with transitional periods and unstable situations within the framework of a transforming society (Zaytseva, 2009). In sociology, individualization is considered as a model of societal anti-risk social engineering, the emphasis of which is placed on multi-variation.

Consequently, the continuity of vocational education is determined by the peculiarity of social reality based on the existence of alternatives that are most likely to be realized in the future. In a situation of alternativeness and uncertainty of living conditions, it is becoming increasingly difficult for the teacher to realize the goals and objectives of education, since the risk field expands when a student selects and implements an individual educational trajectory, moreover, digitization can be considered as one of the complication factors. In this aspect, the following risks can be considered: 1) changes in the actual professional pedagogical space, since digitalization presupposes a different structure and essence of the educational environment; 2) changes in the psycho-physiological characteristics of students (generation Z) and their parents, which requires upgrading the methodology of the educational process and mastering additional pedagogical competencies, 3) a constantly changing list of current professions and competencies in demand in the future; 4) the main teaching tool - communication - acquires new forms.

Digitization generates another feature of the educational process: teacher and student communication through the text, which is defined as the basis of the learning process, even before adults begin to deliberately tell them about technology, complement the knowledge randomly acquired by children from the digital space. This knowledge is transformed into a skill-set, and it becomes sufficient to achieve goals in the world of the future. In addition, along with the hard skills that are associated with specific technologies, in the context of the instability of society, so-called soft skills become the skills of working with algorithms and people. The ability to build logical connections, work in a team and find new and creative solutions is valued in the labor market more and more, since such specialists are easier to learn and adapt to the rapidly changing situation. In addition, the digitalization of life activity generates new types of communications: communication in instant messengers (via a computer interface); communication with the computer (search interfaces) and building communication between two computers to get the desired result (applications on the smartphone: maps, schedule patterns, tips, activity sensors).

In this increasingly complex alternative field, the teacher needs to choose and implement their own lifelong education trajectory, presenting the immediate and prospective risks of dynamically transforming the space of their own life activity, life activity and health of students, their career-oriented success and their own professional success. Accompanying the student in choosing and implementing his individual educational trajectory, the teacher implements taking into account the risks and threats to the student, focusing on the position of the students' parents and the risks that parents see for the successful implementation of the students of their individual educational trajectory. Thus, in continuous pedagogical education in the conditions of digitalization, the problem of riskology is actualized, which is aggravated by additional risks and threats of cyber-socialization as a result of including virtual space as a full-fledged factor of socialization of the individual.

Methodological grounds

Studies of domestic and foreign philosophers, sociologists, psychologists on the problems of

professional and pedagogical foresight, pedagogical riskology, research on the theory of continuous professional education, digitalization of education, analysis of the problem of virtual psychology of childhood and the characteristics of cyber socialization.

Results

When considering the educational process in terms of digitalization, the principle of continuity of vocational and pedagogical education is traditionally considered in the aspect of implementing information technologies, project activities, online education, etc. At the same time, there is enough research on the positive and negative effects of information technologies on psychological and the moral development of schoolchildren, their parents and teachers. It is these changes that should be identified as fundamental in the implementation of continuing professional education, in its essence, content and quality criteria, one of the main ones being the diagnosis and prevention of risks and threats to schoolchildren's life. This idea is reflected in the UNESCO Declaration on Education of the 21st Century, which stresses that the main value of a new culture should be the value of sustainable stable development of a person and society, and the main goal of education is the formation of a viable personality (Shumilova, 2011). In other words, in the basis of continuity of education, the phenomenon of viability should be considered, which is an indicator of the stability of the individual in the conditions of instability of society, and its individualization - as the realization of variability and overcoming the risks of digitalization. In the case when it comes to the continuity of the professional development of the teacher, the viability of the students is both the goal and the indicator of the success of the formation of the viability of the teacher. In this integrity, our research has revealed several contradictions. Consider them in more detail.

Since the viability of the teacher and the student can be viewed as open, self-organizing open systems that operate on the basis of constant information exchange with the environment, as processes of constant translation of meanings and sense-creation. It is logical to assume that indirectly the viability of the teacher and the student is related to their creative abilities, and can be described in the categories of soft skills as the ability to change. (Rylskaya, 2014) And this ability is based on the ability to determine the risks and the vision of options to overcome them.

In the conditions of digitalization, such risks are the threats of bullying, trolling, and the cruelty of students towards each other and to teachers. At the same time, our research shows that parents maintain confidence in the school. Schoolchildren have no confidence in their parents, teachers or classmates. We present the results of the monitoring of the project "Development of normative-methodical proposals for the formalization of non-formal additional education for children", the result of a survey in which parents of 1,375 schoolchildren included in out-of-school activities in 9 districts of Russia, almost 70% of surveyed parents believe showed high confidence in the school (means and to the teacher), noting that a traditional school with a class-less system is able to educate socially active and potentially successful citizens.

Fig.1. The result of a survey of parents in the part “The ability of a modern school to form socially active and potentially successful citizens.” (Where “Да”-“Yes”, “Скорее да”-“rather yes”, “Скорее нет”-“rather no”, “Скорее нет”-“Rather No”, “Нет”-“No”)

At the same time, investigating the subjects of society that are significant for schoolchildren in situations when they learn that their peers are trying drugs, we found out that the teacher is completely absent from the list of subjects of society that are significant for schoolchildren. Those. Speaking of viability as the basis of the continuity of teacher’s professional education, we focus on the significance of its activities for parents and the virtual absence of its importance for schoolchildren. Even more unexpected characteristics of student viability in terms of digitalization (Ivanova, 2015).

Fig. 2. The results of the survey of students on the topic "who can help resolve conflicts in school"

In the virtual space, the communication process of schoolchildren is threatened by the influence of bullying, trolling by both classmates and unknown people, which affects its vitality and requires a well thought-out system to counteract these negative phenomena. (Miroshnichenko, 2009) In our study, we determined that schoolchildren most often encounter trolling (41.7%). The answers to the question of who can help in resolving conflicts in school turned out to be quite revealing: only 8.3% of respondents named teachers, and 79% were not interested in a third party. Thus, it turns out that the schoolchild does not see in the teacher support in resolving conflict situations that bear risks to its viability and prefers advice from third parties offline or unknown persons online. This position carries risks for its viability. This aspect actualizes the change in the essence of the continuity of pedagogical education in the conditions of digitalization, considering it in the context of becoming vitality, which is a characteristic of the teacher’s life potential, which is implemented gradually and is achieved at the stage of maturity, and in the process of information exchange with the environment, based on updating creative activity. In this context, it is important that in the conditions arising in the process of developing a society of new risks, the vitality

function does not manifest itself in a struggle with circumstances, not in existence “in spite of”, not in “coping” (which is typical of resilience and related phenomena) positive, “trans-communicative” relations with the environment and oneself, i.e. the formation of its own harmonious life world (Guryanova, 2004)

Debatable questions. In the virtual space, the communication process of schoolchildren is threatened by the influence of bullying, trolling by both classmates and unknown people, which affects its vitality and requires a well thought-out system to counteract these negative phenomena. (Luginina & Nikitin, 2017) Determining the integrity of the continuity of education of the teacher and his students, we consider it expedient to single out at each of the stages a predictor of vitality: the teacher has spirituality, and the student has self-actualization, allowing to isolate and resist the emergence of viability risks. By combining activity space to solve this problem, we define the mediation space in an educational organization.

The basic principles of modeling such a space:

- the principle of integrity and consistency, the implementation of which includes: prevention and rehabilitation as components of the mediation process, which, in turn, imply a whole complex of integration of educational-supporting, educational, community, family, law enforcement agencies, etc. The systemic interaction of the educational potentials of the subjects of socialization of schoolchildren will ensure the implementation of a “restorative approach” in the mediation process and in the resolution of disputes and conflicts; communicative skills and abilities aimed at comprehensive restoration of relationships, trust, formation (improvement) of adolescent collaboration competencies in real (and not in virtual) communication, etc .;

- The principle of social design, based on the conceptual approaches of the theory of "positive majority" and the principle of "equal to equal" in the search for ways out of conflict or addictive situations (Rylskaya, 2014);

- the principle of axiology – the formation in children and adolescents of values of morally healthy lifestyle, law-abiding, respect for the person, patriotism, etc .;

- The principle of legitimacy – the availability of the necessary legal framework for preventive activities.

- the principle of pedagogical support (tutoring, coaching), which allows considering conflict situations in various spheres of vital activity of minor adolescents as a basis for organizing the process of their recovery in the community and society. The essence of pedagogical mediation is to carry out activities aimed at reducing violent methods of resolving conflicts and precluding the use of restrictive-punitive measures against the violator (Rylskaya, 2014; Shumilova, 2011).

At the basis of the modeling of the mediation space of an educational organization, we define parallel programs for schoolchildren — future members of the mediation group and for teachers. For teachers, the fundamentals of such a program should be based on the foundations of conflict management, riskology, and the psychological characteristics of schoolchildren in a digital environment.

Conclusion

In order to live and successfully work in an extremely mobile and dynamic society of the near future, the teacher and the student must simultaneously have two oppositely directed series of qualities: first, they must have a stable outlook, social and moral convictions, so that on every steep turn of history In a difficult life situation, see options for getting out of the current situation. Secondly, a high psychological liability, flexibility, the ability to assimilate and process new information, master new competencies, be

able to quickly find original solutions, etc., at any age at any stage of life is necessary. The continuity of vocational education of a teacher in terms of digitalization is set by dynamic technical breaking, which influences the development of the psyche of the student and, besides the positive results, creates risks of viability of the student and the success of the professional activity of the teacher.

This is confirmed by the fact that in the process of this article we were diagnosed with a new type of trolling in the educational space: the students stated that teachers constantly express doubts about their abilities, opportunities, prospects, motivating their position by the closeness of adolescents on social networks, gadgets, etc. Of course, such a position does not prevent the viability of adolescents. Our team of authors sees its immediate goal in a detailed study of this phenomenon and the definition of ways and means of countering this position of teachers and the concerns of schoolchildren.

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